

From Wastebin to Wastewater Treatment: Synthesis of Biogenic Carbonate Hydroxyapatite from Eggshells and Its Potential for Lead (Pb^{2+}) Removal

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Abstract

we theorized that employing solid-solid reaction with high-pressure CO_2 at low to medium temperatures using waste eggshells would be ideal for preparing carbonate hydroxyapatite (CHAp) powders. We synthesized bioCHAp from waste eggshells and investigated the performance of the product in the removal of lead (Pb^{2+}) from contaminated (wastewater) water.

The results revealed that eggshells can be recycled to produce type-B bioCHAp with recommended biological apatite carbonate content (3.7 and 7.4 wt %). Furthermore, 40.0 mg of the bioCHAp removed 98.0 % of Pb^{2+} commendably from 200mL of 200mg/L (0.57mol/ml) lead acetate solution within 40 min and 100.0% of the Pb^{2+} in 50 min (half an hour). Interestingly, the bioCHAp also exhibited satisfactory adsorption of Pb^{2+} (85.0 %) in 60 min with 25 mg of the product. Eventually, the 25 mg bioCHAp yielded adsorption capacity of 1360.0 mg/g at equilibrium which is better than values reported for similar works in the literature. The results proved that the synthesized bioCHAp from waste eggshells could also be used as an effective and a cheaper biosorbent for heavy metal (Pb^{2+}) removal.

Keywords: carbonated hydroxylapatite; wastewater treatment, lead, eggshells, Wastebin

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has shown that carbonated hydroxylapatite (CHAp) is an important inorganic calcium-phosphate material (Marchat et al., 2007; Rauschmann et al., 2005; Tomoda et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2011; Baillez et al., 2007; Mizushima et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2010). Accordingly, many researchers have devoted their energies towards developing protocols for the synthesis and application of these materials (Lin et al., 2011; Meski et al., 2010; Kim and Kim, 2012; Rovensky et al., 2003). Producing CHAp materials from waste eggshells has been attractive due to the inherent advantages in the use of the waste product (Rauschmann et al., 2005; ; Meski et al., 2010; Rovensky et al., 2003; Ibrahim et al., 2015; Ripamonti et al., 2009; Vecchio et al., 2007). The eggshell constitutes about 11% of the overall weight of the egg (Rovensky et al., 2003). Due to this, waste eggshells are a nuisance to deal with especially, for developing countries in Africa. For instance, even

though there is no reliable data on the production of eggs in Ghana, the consumption of eggs in the country is increasing due to the proliferation of mini and medium 'indomie' fast food enterprises in recent times. These fast food vendors use eggs as the main protein source; and a serving may contain at least two eggs. There also tea vendors at the various transport stations and other vantage points all over the towns, serving tea to travellers and other customers. A serving in this case usually involves the tea with bread and at least two fried eggs. And then, there are domestic egg consumers.

Clearly, waste eggshells from the use of egg products will continue to increase in Ghana. Traditionally, we have practically no use of the waste eggshells. Hence, obtaining better and effective applications for waste eggshells is paramount. Synthesis of calcium-phosphate products from waste eggshells has usually been through the sol-gel and wet solution techniques (Liu et al., 2002; Zhang et al., 2007; Cheng et al., 2003). However, the use of supercritical CO₂ has been explored (McCool and Tripp, 2004).

Only recently, we synthesized CHAp from waste eggshells with supercritical CO₂ and obtained products with larger surface properties (surface area and pore volume). The product was used as a drug (Ibuprofen) delivery agent with excellent results (Ibrahim et al., 2019). In this study however, we investigated the performance of the synthesized bioCHAp product in the removal of lead (Pb²⁺) from wastewater.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Commercial Ca(OH)₂, Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O, Pb(C₂H₃O₂)₂, Ethanol and CO₂ (99.99%) gas were purchased from JAIF, a local Medical supply vendor in Tamale. Waste eggshells were obtained from random food vendors in the Tamale Metropolis. The waste eggshells were pretreated as reported earlier (Ibrahim et al., 2013).

2.2 Biogenic Ca(OH)₂

The waste eggshells were washed to remove dirt, dried at 80 °C overnight and transformed into CaO powder for subsequent use. The CaO powder upon storage was transformed into pure Ca(OH)₂ (Figure 1) which is referred to as biogenic Ca(OH)₂ hereafter, and was used to produce the biogenic CHAp products (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

Figure 1. XRD patterns for a): commercial Ca(OH)₂, b): raw eggshells, c): calcined eggshells and d): biogenic Ca(OH)₂

2.3 Biogenic CHAp product

The biogenic CHAp product was produced following the procedure reported earlier (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Appropriate mass of the biogenic Ca(OH)₂ and the phosphate precursor (Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O) corresponding to Ca/P mole ratio of 1.67 were placed in a reaction vessel (100 ml) and reacted in the presence of CO₂.

Meanwhile, the reaction was continuously stirred gently (10 rpm) in a water bath. The resulting products were washed thoroughly and dried at 80 °C overnight and labeled as bioCHAp (Figure 2).

2.4 Characterization

The biogenic products were also characterized by XRD (Rigaku Ultima IV), SEM (Hitachi, S-4800), BET (Micromeritics ASAP 2020, USA) and XRF (S8 Tiger, Germany) as reported (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

2.5 Pb²⁺ adsorption

The adsorption experiments were conducted as reported elsewhere (Ibrahim, et al., 2013). The aim was to investigate whether or not the bioCHAp produced could facilitate effective Pb²⁺ adsorption. An amount (40.0mg) of the bioCHAp with the best properties (212.4m²/g surface area and 0.65 cm³/g pore volume) without calcination was added into 200mL of 200mg/L (0.57mol/ml) lead acetate (Pb(C₂H₃O₂)₂) aqueous solution at pH of 6 under gentle agitation (10rpm) at room temperature (25⁰C). 10 ml of the suspension at given intervals was filtered through a membrane filter and diluted with nitric acid (HNO₃) in order to determine the Pb²⁺ concentration. Separation was done by centrifugation and Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, PerkinElmer 700) was used to analyze the dissolved Pb²⁺ using a calibration curve (Ibrahim, et al., 2013). The adsorption isotherms were measured as reported (Ibrahim, et al., 2015).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We theorized that employing solid-solid reaction with high-pressure CO₂ at low to medium temperatures using waste eggshells would be ideal for preparing carbonate-hydroxyapatite (CHAp) powders. However, the use of this procedure has not been reported in the literature prior to our earlier report (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Yet, high-pressure CO₂ has low viscosity but relatively high diffusivity which guarantees better transport properties because of easier and faster diffusion through solid reactants when used as a solvent and reaction media (McCool and Tripp, 2005).

3.1 Phase and Purity Analysis

Phase composition analysis was achieved by XRD as reported (Ibrahim et al., 2019). The XRD patterns for the intermediate product before washing and the final CHAp product after washing are shown in Figure 2. Rietveld analysis revealed that there was complete conversion of the biogenic Ca(OH)₂ with production of pure bioCHAp (ICSD-PDF2: 00-019-0272) at 10.0MPa and 40. □ °C in 30min.

Figure 2. XRD patterns for product from biogenic Ca(OH)₂ and Na₂HPO₄

The complete conversion of the biogenic Ca(OH)₂ to pure bioCHAp may be due to the nature of the biogenic Ca(OH)₂. It was obtained from raw eggshells which were calcined for 5h at 950°C. Organics in the eggshells were completely burnt and the shells were transformed into pure CaO powder (Figure 1). The transformation afforded the biogenic Ca(OH)₂ loose structure packing compared to a commercial Ca(OH)₂ (Figure 3) such that the loosely packed biogenic Ca(OH)₂ could be accessed easily by water/CO₂ (or both) for subsequent

dissolutions and reactions, leading to the complete conversion. Rietveld refinements from XRD analysis revealed that type-B bioCHAp was synthesized; functional group analysis confirmed that type-B bioCHAp was produced and Stability analysis also showed that the bioCHAp product was stable as in the previous report (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

3.2 Morphology Analysis

SEM images for the commercial and the biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and the bioCHAp are shown in Figure 3. The images of the biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ itself showed agglomerated but caterpillar-like particles (Figure 3) however, the images from Na_2HPO_4 produced with the biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ were cotton-like and flower-like nanostructures (< 10nm).

Figures 3. SEM images for a): commercial $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ b): biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ from eggshells and c): bioCHAp produced at 10.0 MPa and 40.0 °C in 30min

3.3 Carbonate content

In the previous report (Ibrahim et al., 2019), we estimated the carbonate content based on XRF analysis (Othman et al., 2013). The products yielded the carbonate contents within the recommended biological apatite carbonate values (4–8 wt %) for medical applications (Othman et al., 2013). In the current report, the carbonate content (wt %) in the bioCHAp was estimated based on analyses of the ratio of the FTIR (Figure 4) band areas from Eqn.1 (Grunenwald et al., 2014) and shown in Table 1.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra for a typical bioCHAp obtained in 30 min at 40.0°C and 10.0 MPa

$$[\text{CO}_3 (\text{wt}\%)] = 28.62 \left[\frac{V_3(\text{CO}_3)}{V_3V_1(\text{PO}_4)} \right] + 0.0843 \quad (1)$$

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$V_3(\text{CO}_3)$ is the area of the well-defined CO_3^{2-} band from FTIR spectrum between $900\text{-}1230\text{cm}^{-1}$ wave number whereas $V_3V_1(\text{PO}_4)$ is the area of PO_4^{3-} bands between $1330\text{-}1570\text{cm}^{-1}$ wave number estimated with OMNIC 8.2 software after automatic baseline correction (Grunenwald et al., 2014).

Table 1. Estimation of carbonate content of bioCHAp based on FTIR spectra

Experiment	$V_3(\text{CO}_3)$	$V_3V_1(\text{PO}_4)$	Carbonate Content
1	109.76	810.21	4.0
2	126.98	999.53	3.7
3	102.99	590.56	5.1
4	126.08	492.03	7.4
5 ^a	242.76	971.21	7.2
6	123.8	518.07	6.9

^athe best BET surface area for the bioCHAp synthesized was $212.4\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ with pore volume of $0.65\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$ (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

The biogenic product in the current study also yielded carbonate contents (Table 1) within the recommended biological apatite carbonate values (4–8 wt %) for medical applications (Othman et al., 2013).

3.4 Effect of water

The mechanism for the synthesis of the bioCHAp is the same as we reported (Ibrahim et al., 2019), which is similar to the mechanism proposed for the self-catalytic reaction of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in supercritical CO_2 for producing CaCO_3 (Ibrahim et al., 2013). Specifically, appropriate amount of water on the surfaces of the solid reactants acts as catalyst and triggers the initial reaction, and enhances the reaction after its (water) production (Ibrahim et al., 2019). However, less amount of water ($< 0.40\text{ mol}$) would starve the reaction of reacting species and yield poor conversion as reported (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

Figure 5. Effect of removal of water on surface of reactants before and after washing, indicating incomplete conversion: b): $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, c): HAp and d): CHAp

In the current study, the reactants (biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were dried at 100°C for 48h to remove water molecules on the surfaces prior to the reaction in 30 min at 40.0°C and 10.0 MPa . The conversion was very poor (30%) compared to complete conversion without the drying treatment, indicating the importance

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of water molecules on the surfaces of the reactants. Even so, the major phase produced was HAp (01-073-1731) with trace of CHAp (Figure 5). The available water adsorbed on the surface of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (0.221 mg/mg) stored for a month and on $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.582mg/mg) is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. TG curves showing weight loss attributed to water molecules from solid (i): $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (ii): biogenic $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ at 900°C for 5h; sample stored for (a): 1 month and (b): more than 6 months with corresponding amount of water per gram of sample

3.5. Biogenic adsorbent

Larger surface area and pore properties are vital for application of nanomaterials. They are important in drug loading and delivery (Ibrahim et al., 2019). They are equally important in the adsorption of heavy metals from industrial and contaminated aqueous solutions.

The adsorption of Pb^{2+} from aqueous solution by the bioCHAp (Figure 7) showed that about 98.0% of Pb^{2+} was removed within 40 min and 100.0% of the Pb^{2+} was removed 10 min later when 40.0mg of the biogenic adsorbent (bioCHAp) was used with the 200mL of 200mg/L (0.57mol/ml) lead acetate solution at pH of 6 under gentle agitation (20rpm) at 25°C.

Figure 7. Adsorption profile for Pb^{2+} by bioCHAp at room temperature

However, the adsorption (Figure 7) showed that about 85.0% of Pb^{2+} was removed within 60 min when 25.0mg of the biosorbent (bioCHAp) was used. These results indicate that the effect of the bioCHAp as biosorbent (for Pb adsorption) was dependent on the amount of the sample and by extension, the surface and pore properties (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

The adsorption capacity (q_t) in mg Pb^{2+} /g of the bioCHAp at arbitrary time, t , was calculated based on **Eqn. 2** as reported earlier (Ibrahim et al., 2015).

$$q_t = (c_0 - c_t)v / m \quad (2)$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of Pb^{2+} in the $Pb(AC)_2$ solution (mg/l), C_t is the concentration of Pb^{2+} in the solution (mg/l) at arbitrary time t , V is the volume of solution (L), and m is the weight of adsorbent used (g). The adsorption model for the bioCHAp-Pb system was accurately described by the Langmuir isotherm model using **Eqn. 3** as reported in earlier studies (Kaludjerovic-Radoicica and Raicevic, 2010; Zheng et al., 2007).

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_m} C_e + \frac{1}{q_m K_L} \quad (3)$$

Where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of Pb^{2+} in the $Pb(AC)_2$ solution (mg/l), q_e is the equilibrium adsorption capacity (mg Pb^{2+} /g bioCHAp), q_m is the maximum adsorption (mg/g) and K_L is the Langmuir constant.

The adsorption capacity (q_e) for the 25 mg CHAp used with the 200mL of 200mg/L (0.57mol/ml) lead acetate solution at equilibrium was thus calculated to be 1360.0mg/g. This value is better than values reported for similar works in the literature (Kumar et al., 2013; Baillez et al., 2007).

IR spectra revealed similarity between the functional groups of the bioCHAp (Figure 2) and the bioCHAp-Pb (Figure 8) from the adsorption, indicating that there was ion exchange during the adsorption process (Ibrahim et al., 2013; Ibrahim et al., 2015).

Figure 8. FTIR spectra for the bioCHAp-Pb from the adsorption process

4. CONCLUSIONS

We theorized that employing solid-solid reaction with high-pressure CO_2 at low to medium temperatures using waste eggshells would be ideal for preparing carbonate-hydroxyapatite (CHAp) powders. We investigated the performance of the synthesized bioCHAp product in the removal of lead (Pb) from contaminated (waste) water.

Based on the results, we conclude that the eggshells can be recycled to produce type-B bioCHAp with recommended biological apatite carbonate content (3.7 and 7.4 wt %). Furthermore, the bioCHAp exhibited satisfactory adsorption of Pb^{2+} (85.0 %) from aqueous lead acetate solution in 60 min with 25mg of the product. However, 40.0mg of the bioCHAp removed 98.0% of Pb^{2+} within 40 min and 100.0% of the Pb^{2+} in 50 min. Eventually, the 25 mg bioCHAp yielded adsorption capacity (q_e) of 1360.0 mg/g at equilibrium, better than values reported for similar works in the literature.

The results proved that the synthesized bioCHAp from waste eggshells could also be used as effective and cheaper biosorbent for heavy metal (Pb^{2+}) removal since the removal of lead (Pb^{2+}) from contaminated drinking and wastewaters is very important.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests

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